

Question Cards

- Facts
- Feelings
- Benefits
- Process
- Creative
- Cautions

Value Dimensions

- Quality & Validation
- Customer goodwill
- Peer to peer support
- Branding value
- Outsource your innovation
- Test ideas with the community
- Make co-creation & participation easy
- Insight about costumers & co-creation
- Build on knowledge of global innovators
- Reduce development costs

